
The Quest for Racial Identity in *Black Skin, White Masks* by Frantz Fanon and the Novels of James Baldwin

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ABSTRACT

Blackness plays a critical role in the works of Baldwin and Fanon. The scope of anti-black racism is the effective core of racial oppression, withal historical perspective of Baldwin and Fanon specifies European and American white people's role in the world today. Questions of race, history, and oppressed peoples' rights is the question of memory in the realm of cultural history that both Baldwin and Fanon are investigating accordingly. Baldwin breaks the question of the status of cultural forms from Fanon by anti-black racist regimes. Fanon's Sartreanism reflected as the break with history, and the abjection of memory emphasized the preciousness of the future. Baldwin's account of African-American life under regimes of anti-black racism is merely the meaning of the imagined future. Baldwin and Fanon begin with the situatedness of the existential condition of irreducible non-belonging and discuss anti-racist struggle in search of finding a place to be lived.

INTRODUCTION

Frantz Fanon (1925-61), psychoanalyst and social philosopher, influenced the following generations of social activists and thinkers. Fanon leaves the French colony of Martinique, and his works are influential in the fields of post-colonial studies and critical theory. He leaves Martinique for Algeria, from a diagnosis of the Martiniquan situation, and Baldwin leaves Harlem in the United States to live in France. Darbinski illustratively shows Fanon and Baldwin do not "appeal to the cultural subconscious of an Africanist life philosophy; black culture, and so a sense of connection and fecund relation that would generate the feeling and meaning of home, cannot (and even should not) be revitalized by its re-Africanization." (Darbinski,139) He continues, "Baldwin places black people at the heart of the logic of home-making in the United States, rather than placing black people, as Fanon does, outside the national and cultural rhetoric of colonial identity." Unlike Fanon for whom "the black subject is lost in the colonizer's world—disoriented by the weight of a total project of domination—Baldwin claims an interdependency of white Americans on black abjections that exceeds Fanon's (and Césaire's) claim that the colonizer is also harmed by colonialism." (*Ibid.*,141)

James Baldwin (1924-87) was one of the most influential artists of the post-Second World War generation who was born in Harlem, New York City.

In youth, he sailed to France, for good. He felt that socially America was too oppressive, both because he was black and homosexual. That was the reason he did not back to the U.S. again. In the collected political and autobiographical collection of essays called *The Price of the Ticket*, Baldwin has created a long-term effect on American social life, especially in the area of race relations. Baldwin brings us back to his experience in France, a country he considers as a free land from the narrowing racial and identical sexual categories that affected postwar America. "It was a society," Baldwin writes of the United States, "in which nothing was fixed, and we had therefore been born to a greater number of possibilities, wretched as these possibilities seemed at the instant of our birth." (*Baldwin, 1985d, 45*) In *The Fire Next Time*, Baldwin wrote, "I knew the tension in me between love and power, between pain and rage, and the curious, the grinding way I remained extended between these poles—perpetually attempting to choose the better rather than the worse" (*Ibid.*, 60).

Fanon in *Black Skin, White Masks*, makes his phenomenological analysis of diction and alienation and Baldwin in "Princes and Powers," is underlying the experience of blackness in "an anti-black racist world, the rage and grievance levelled against those who have cause unspeakable pain, and a sense of shared identity in this shared experience, rage, and grievance." (Darbinski,139) Darbinski wrote, "Anti-black racism is a total project—whether that project

is manifest in the plantation, colonial relations, or the simple violent hostility of the (white) society in which black subjects live," (*Ibid.*,126) and continues, "Morality and ontology intersect at the origin-point of the psyche. Black subjectivity is morally complicated from the outset, and the social, cultural, and political structures of subjugation and marginalization confirm and reproduce that wounded identity at every turn." (*Ibid.*,132)

Baldwin is Delineating Racial Identity

James Baldwin, the Exile and the New Diaspora are interrelated. Baldwin's power is his ability to express the situation of being a Negro and a human being therewithal. Once Baldwin wrote in *The New York Times*, "I am speaking of the beginning of the end of the black diaspora, which means that I am speaking of the beginning of the end of the world as we have suffered it until now." (Baldwin, 1976, 1) In response to the 1956 Negro Writers and Artists' Congress in Paris, Baldwin aroused the synonymousness of pain and home in his essay "Princes and Powers" which gave justification to the Pan-Africanist vision of homelessness. He says,

Moreover, the land of our forefathers' exile had been made, by that travail, our home. It may have been the popular impulse to keep us at the bottom of the perpetually shifting and bewildered populace; but we were, on the other hand, almost personally indispensable to each of them, simply because, without us, they could never have been certain, in such a confusion, where the bottom was; and nothing, in any case, could take away our title to the land which we, too, had purchased with our blood. (Baldwin, 1985d, 45)

Go Tell It on the Mountain made Baldwin one of the great observers of the American racial situation. It is primarily about someone's quest to find out who he is. The characters in this book are black, and they seldom relate with white characters unless there is an issue. Race concept here is a tool to highlight characteristics, and blacks' personality is shown against white people. Despite a few positive white characters shown here, Baldwin does not aim to portray reality, or explains how things look within a closed community. In the novel, the Harlem area of New York City—where the Grimes family lives—is internationally famous for the African-American neighborhood with a rich cultural history at the beginning of the twentieth century. By

the years this novel takes place, the former centre of culture was on its way to becoming an international symbol of poverty. "For black is the color of evil," Baldwin writes, "only the robes of the saved are white. It is this cry, implacable on the air and in the skull, that he must live with" (Baldwin, 1985b, 32-33). In an underestimated essay, "Encounter on the Seine: Black Meets Brown," Baldwin wrote:

The American Negro cannot explain to the African what surely seems in himself to be a want of manliness, of racial pride, a maudlin ability to forgive. It is difficult to make clear that he is not seeking to forfeit his birthright as a black man, but that, on the contrary, it is precisely this birthright which he is struggling to recognize and make articulate. Perhaps it now occurs to him that in this need to establish himself in relation to his past he is most American, that this depthless alienation from oneself and one's people is, in sum, the American experience. (Baldwin, 1985a,39)

Baldwin theorises the white man as a problem and finds it as "the peculiar triumph of society—and its loss—that it is able to convince those people to whom it has given inferior status of the reality of this decree; it has the force and the weapons to translate its dictum into fact, so that the allegedly inferior are actually made so ... [W]e find ourselves bound, first without, then within, by the nature of our categorization." (Baldwin, 1985b, 32) Baldwin's long essay *The Fire Next Time* shows the cruelty of poverty and violence. He wrote, "In the same way that we, for white people, were the descendants of Ham, and were cursed forever, white people were, for us, the descendants of Cain. And the passion with which we loved the Lord was a measure of how deeply we feared and distrusted and, in the end, hated almost all strangers, always, and avoided and despised ourselves." (Baldwin, 2004, 40-41)

For Africans, Afro-Caribbean and African-Americans in the narrow, France where Baldwin arrived during and after the Second World War, signified a space free from the racist and racial problems of their home countries. The matter theoretically united the various groups was the shared experience of exile and being isolated from home, America, and not thoroughly combined into French society—a feeling that diaspora blacks already knew too well. Baldwin's French exile was likewise a flight from a space in which he felt alienated; mainly as a black man and a homosexual. Baldwin wrote, "How can the American Negro's past

be used? The unprecedented price demanded—and at this embattled hour of the world’s history—is the transcendence of the realities of color, of nations, and of altars.” (Baldwin, 1985d, 103)

In addition to the shocking suicide of a close friend, Eugene, Baldwin fictionalized his self-imposed exile in the opening chapter of his third novel, *Another Country*. During the two decades he spent in France, he visited many lands of Europe, Asia, and the United States. Baldwin wrote and published most of his novels and essays that not directly reflect extremely American themes in general, and a black homosexual American in particular, but also the exile experience of particularly Americans in France. Baldwin concludes *The Fire Next Time* with a famous evocation:

When I was very young, and was dealing with my buddies in those wine- and urine-stained hall-ways, something in me wondered, What will happen to all that beauty? For black people, though I am aware that some of us, black and white, do not know it yet, are very beautiful ... [Vengeance], I wondered, when that vengeance was achieved, What will happen to all that beauty then? ... If we—and now I mean the relatively conscious whites and the relatively conscious blacks, who must, like lovers, insist on, or create, the consciousness of the others—do not falter in our duty now, we may be able, handful that we are, to end the racial nightmare, and achieve our country, and change the history of the world. (*Ibid.*, 104-105)

Baldwin’s biography and essays, and above all *Giovanni’s Room*, seriously attempted to show exile as a key theme, in which through the portrayal of the Parisian locations, the city itself, the gay bars, and Giovanni’s Room, and their contrast with American locations, Baldwin shows the function of exile and otherness through sexual identities. *Giovanni’s Room* has primarily been focused on displacement of blackness unto whiteness, and stage a murdering party to discover and picture the critical look of the black man in the text. Thoroughly, Baldwin finds a connection between the state of being in exile and the state of sexual identity. Although the novel begins and ends with David standing by the window of a house in the South of France, the first section of the novel takes us in his memory, back to the U.S. of his childhood and youth, and his reasons for being a refugee in

France. Baldwin’s experience of Paris during the 1940s to 1960s is useful in analysing the function of the city in his work. However, David’s whiteness stops much of the possible parallels between the author’s and the character’s interests for exile: while Baldwin left the U.S to find a racial and sexual haven, David has logical not racial reasons for fleeing the U.S.

[The] condition and situation of black subjectivity fundamentally alters the ecstatic structure of affective life precisely because the meaning of home is at stake. To wit: if we presume a sense of belonging, then the tension of subjectivity in ecstatic affective life is initiated by the loss of or threat to a sense of home. However, if we begin with the alienation produced by anti-black racism, then ecstatic affective life, as its originary condition, is suspended between the reactive structure of rage and pain—the fundamental objection to persecution and hatred—and the aspirational structure of a wanting to belong and desiring a place. Baldwin is always careful to prescribe this wanting and desire without an appeal to white ideality (Darbinski, 137-8).

Fanon is a Revolutionary Warrior of Racial Liberation

Frantz Fanon’s literary and philosophical odyssey started with a personal confrontation of his blackness in a white world and led him to the war of liberation of his adopted home, Algeria. He developed a revolutionary theory that seemed relevant to Africa—if not to all the Third World—and influenced liberation politics among colonised nations. As his involvement in the Algerian revolution increased, he became a writer, propagandist, spokesperson, and diplomat for the Front de Libération National (FLN), as well as a theorist of anticolonial revolution. Fanon participated and arrayed his essay “Racism and Culture” in the 1956 conference about the national culture and the new humanism in *The Wretched of the Earth*. After his death at age thirty-six, his book *The Wretched of the Earth* had a substantial impact on Third World politics. Fanon joined the Algerian Nationalist Movement at the time Algeria was being colonised by France. The violence which is described in *The Wretched of the Earth* reflects the struggle for independence in Algeria, and the writing is sympathetic towards colonised natives.

Fanon also became the leading figure for the Black Power movement in the United States during the 1960s and later. It was mainly because of his book *Black Skin, White Masks: The Experiences of a Black Man in a White World*, in theoretical dialogues on identity politics and postcolonial theory. Fanon argues that the decolonization must always be a violent event because fighting a colonising power by using sole politics will not be effective. Fanon locates the problem of identity in language which is the intimate subject related to the concept of consciousness and world. Fanon criticizes cultural and political forces as not only sites of diagnosis, but also the most intimate sites of identity in subjective life.

Without being occupied, the land would not be influential to make money and would go back to the middle ages. God's good work requires white men to impose their European religion, medicines, and civilisation onto natives that are approved as evil. Because of the disease they carried and their underdeveloped technology and weaponry, the natives were called "savages" or "primitive". Thus and so, settlers consider native's anger as evil acts against God and natives see the settlers as the bringers of violence. Settlers would forcefully take lands that belong to other people to force their native country's politics. Later, in *Black Skin, White Masks*, Fanon writes: "What's all this about black people and a black nationality? I am French. I am interested in French culture, French civilization, and the French. We refuse to be treated as outsiders; we are well and truly part of French history and its drama [...] I take a personal interest in the destiny of France, the French nation, and its values. What am I supposed to do with a black empire?" (Fanon, 2008, 179)

Colonialism, what Fanon calls the inferiority complex is more than an imposition by physical or political force. Europeans believed that God wanted to occupy all lands and spread the word of god to savages of darker skin colour. Fanon claims that decolonisation causes violent actions to both settlers and natives. Violence from Europeans during the colonisation was to control and silent the natives and opposition. The police and soldiers of the settlers used excessive force to show dominance. European churches, schools, and societies were set up on colonised lands. Native uprisings would rarely change anything politically; it gave individuals a short-term feeling that they were not second-rate to their oppressors by the beginning disorder. The anger that crazed for their oppressors was uttered through crime and battles with other native tribes. European settlers believed that by some godly right, all lands were created for them as their native country. Fanon finds it a reason to ignore their oppressors, accept colonisation

of their land, and to allow history to move on. Fanon wrote, "The North African does not come with a substratum common to his race, but on a foundation built by the European. In other words, the North African, spontaneously, by the very act of appearing on the scene, enters into a pre-existing framework. (Fanon, 1994, 7)

Frantz Fanon stated psychiatric notes about the effects of the war on the native people. Lack of dignity, depression, weakness, suicidal and violence were psychiatric disorders developed by colonised people to make an end in their lifestyle accomplished through extreme violence, raping, and murder of the native people. Thus, decolonisation causes violence and anger from both settlers and natives. Settlers see violence as an effective way of conquering new land and to regain their freedom. Violence from both settlers and natives during a period of decolonisation supports Fanon's argument. *Black Skin, White Masks* (1952) by Fanon in the style of auto-theory is a historical critique of the effects of anti-black racism and colonial domination on the human psyche to change the life of black subjectivity.

The power of *Black Skin, White Masks* lies in its review into the black man's experience of blackness which describes a white European child who cries, "Mama, see the Negro! I'm frightened!" (Fanon, 2008, 84) This moment re-creates for the recognition of the category of black and the association of fear with it. At the same time, they determine a condition of otherness from whites that both generates and defines other opposition ideas. Fanon starts by telling the reasons he wrote the book and reveals a difficulty for persons of colour by analysing the effects of racial arrogance. The depth and strength of his character is reflected through diverse in psychology, sociology, literary criticism, economics, and politics. Fanon as a psychiatrist and revolutionary shared his ideas in Algeria. The ideas in *The Wretched of the Earth* is applied to all colonised nations, especially those in Africa.

[To] put it in Fanon's terms, the Nation's reversal of racist terms only confirms the terms of anti-black racism by reifying, in the black power gesture of superiority, the Manichean structure of raciological thinking. That is, the Nation merely reverses the terms of inferiority. While this surely labors against the affective elements of the inferiority complex and, in perhaps the best feature of black nationalism, promises to challenge the ideologically-laden structures of poverty and violence [...] the

Manichean structure of social relations remain intact. (Darbinski, 134)

Fanon begins with the violence of colonisation. Since colonisation is a violent phenomenon, violence is a means to an end of colonialism and revelling the oppressed from the psychological and physical chains of colonialism. Although Fanon addressed his book to the peoples of the Third World, the African peasants and nationalists took little note of his ideas. However, the negative patterns that he forecast, quickly came true in post-colonial Africa.

The relations between racism and social justice, studies of the mingling of politics and economics between coloniser and colonised, developed and underdeveloped worlds are explored in Fanon's books. Fanon mentions that he was well familiar with the history of colonisation and Third World movements. Becoming politically independent, new nations found themselves dependent upon the former colonial powers' economic power. Using this dependency, the former colonial powers used their force to gain natural resources from the developing nations. Continued economically dependent relationships are called "neocolonial" because they show the maintenance of colonisation by different means. Fanon was introducing a central philosophical principle: decolonisation is a necessary and historical part of the dialectic. It is the logical process of the struggle of opposites in time. Fanon writes:

Every human problem cries out to be considered on the basis of time, the ideal being that the present always serves to build the future.

And this future is not that of the cosmos, but very much the future of my century, my country, and my existence. In no way is it up to me to prepare for the world coming after me. I am resolutely a man of my time.

And that is my reason for living. The future must be a construction supported by man in the present. This future edifice is linked to the present insofar as I consider the present something to be overtaken." (Fanon, 2008, xvi-xvii)

History is the source of pain and Fanon and Baldwin are suffering the psyche to the past. Language is an effective element in discussing black subjectivity by imagining an ideal world. Fanon in the closing line to

"Racism and Culture" takes us to the future without a past, "a language in which it is already spoken, if not yet heard" (Darbinski, 156) Fanon moreover says speaking "means being able to use a certain syntax and possessing the morphology of such and such a language, but it means above all assuming a culture and bearing the weight of a civilization" (Fanon, 2008, 1-2). Baldwin wrote the matter brings about all languages and all men, is "the necessity to confront life, in order, not inconceivably, to outwit death: The price for this is the acceptance, and achievement, of one's temporal identity." He continues, "language is also a political instrument, means, and proof of power. It is the most vivid and crucial key to identity: It reveals the private identity, and connects one with, or divorces one from, the larger, public, or communal identity." (Fanon, 1985c, 650) Darbinski explicitly describes that "if language alienates in the colonial relation, and language is situated at the foundations of thinking and being, then the event of language is the event of the coming into being of the psyche. Thoroughly, colonialism wounds from the very outset. To be colonized is to be wounded. The wound does its work in the affective structures that structure relations to thinking, being, embodiment, identity, and so on. In other words, colonization is a total project." (Daibinski, 131) He says humanity sets up "home—the psyche—in language," wherein that home, or language, "an image is produced in the racist imaginary that wounds or amputates black subjectivity at the heart of what it means to be." (*Ibid.*, 132-3)

CONCLUSION

Colonialism in Fanonian works, and violence and racial segregation in Baldwin's works are submitters of their ideology. Flinch of history and memory by Fanon contrasts with retrieval of the cultural complexity by Baldwin. For Baldwin, the meaning of home bears upon the history and humanity's geography of thinking. The legacy of anti-black racism and the revolution against anti-black racism are the main themes of Fanon and Baldwin's works. Fanon identifies struggle consciously by reintroducing the meaning of revolution, and Baldwin works in the question of home and context of the United States—where thoroughly sets the terms of black liberation. Baldwin is not radical enough in issues of racism and echoes Fanon's foundational ideological structure of racism through the elements of poverty and violence. Baldwin reminds us that the imagination has never been fully bound by abjection of history we find in Fanon. In "Everybody's Protest Novel," he explains that we can read the interval between past and future

simply. It is a kind of theoretical protest to deny dread and power.

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